

A Comparative Study to Evaluate Efficacy of Olopatadine Eye Drops and Bepotastine Eye Drops in Cases of Vernal Kerato Conjunctivitis

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ABSTRACT

Aim: To evaluate efficacy of Olopatadine eye drops in comparison to Bepotastine eye drops in cases of Vernal Kerato Conjunctivitis. **Materials and Methods:** This is a Prospective, Randomised, Observational Study conducted at the department of Ophthalmology of a tertiary eye care hospital. 50 cases of newly diagnosed VKC who were more than 5 years of age were selected for the study. Cases who were already on treatment and cases who were having other ocular disorders, Contact lens users and those whose parents and gaurdians had not given consent were excluded. 50 cases selected were randomly divided based on even and Odd MR No. into 2 groups. Informed consent obtained from parents of all patients. All were examined by an experienced Ophthalmologist using, Snellen's chart, Slit Lamp, Direct Ophthalmoscope, 90 D Slit lamp Bio microscopy. Baseline score were recorded based on Symptoms like Itching, Watering, Redness, FB sensation and Signs like Hyperaemia, Discharge, Papillae on tarsal conjunctiva and Tranta's spot at the Limbus. Group A consist of patients who were given Olopatadine eye drops to be instilled 3 times daily for 6 weeks. Group B consist of VKC patients who were given Bepotastine eye drops to be instilled twice daily for 6 weeks. Both group were called for Follow up after 1 week, 2 weeks and 6 weeks. Patients were asked about relief from Symptomatology and examined for regression of Signs at each visit. **Results:** 50 cases selected for study were aged between 5-15years. 5-10 years there were 36 cases and between 10-15 years 14 cases were there. Sex distribution was 39 males and 11 females. In group B relief from symptoms like Itching, Watering and FB sensation were achieved on second visit in most of the patients. Whereas in Group A the patients were having Symptomatology and signs persisted till 3rd visit. **Conclusion:** Bepotastine eye drops appeared to be more effective in controlling Symptoms and Regression of Signs.

Keywords: VKC, Itching, Watering, FB sensation, Discharge, Hyperaemia, Papillary Hypertrophy and Tranta's spot.

INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of allergic diseases among school children is gradually increasing and varies from 0.3% to 20.5%. Ocular allergy is one of the most common types of allergies. Allergic conjunctivitis in India, stands as the second most common reason of ocular morbidity and comprises almost 15-20% cases attending ophthalmology clinics. It is usually associated with other allergic diseases. The term allergic conjunctivitis includes Seasonal allergic conjunctivitis (SAC), Perennial allergic conjunctivitis (PAC), Vernal kerato conjunctivitis (VKC), and Atopic kerato conjunctivitis (AKC).

Vernal catarrh or vernal keratoconjunctivitis (VKC) comprises 0.5% of allergic eye disease¹. VKC most commonly occurs in boys living in warm, dry, subtropical climates, such as the Mediterranean, the Middle East, Central and West Africa, South America, and Asian countries, such as Japan, Thailand, and India. The limbal form of VKC is seen most often in dark-skinned individuals from Africa and India. VKC is a chronic, bilateral, at times asymmetrical, seasonally exacerbated, allergic inflammation of the ocular surface, involving tarsal and/or bulbar conjunctiva. It is an IgE- and T cell-

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mediated disease, leading to a chronic inflammation in which eosinophil, lymphocyte and structural cell activation characterize the conjunctival allergic reaction. VKC is characterised by giant papillae found in either the upper tarsal conjunctiva or at the limbus². VKC is more complex than a mere type 1 hypersensitivity reaction. Many clinical and experimental studies about the cells and mediators

involved in initiating and perpetuating the ocular allergic inflammation have shown that T helper type 2 cells and their cytokines, corneal fibroblasts and epithelium along with various growth factors play an important role in the pathogenesis of VKC.

Scoring of VKC based on signs and symptoms

Variable	Score			
	0	1	2	3
Symptom				
Itching	None	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Tearing	None	Wet eye without tears on face	Intermittent tears on face	Constant tears on face
Signs				
Conjunctival Hyperaemia	None	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Tarsal Papillae	None	<1mm	1-3mm	>3mm
Limbal papillae	None	<90 ⁰ or <2mm	90 ⁰ -180 ⁰ or 2-4mm	>180 ⁰ or >4mm

Table 2 Scoring of signs and symptoms of Vernal kerato conjunctivitis⁴

New antihistamines that combine mast cell stabilizing properties and histamine receptor antagonism, such as alcaftadine, azelastine, bepotastine, epinastine, ketotifen, and olopatadine, are presently available. The advantage offered by these agents is the rapidity of symptomatic relief given by immediate histamine receptor antagonism, which alleviates itching and redness, coupled with the long-term disease-modifying benefit of mast cell stabilization⁵.

Olopatadine (0.1%) is a selective H1 antagonist with mast-cell-stabilizing properties. Olopatadine, in addition to stabilizing mast cells, affects the release of TNF- α and various cytokines from conjunctival epithelial cells, thus controlling the allergic inflammation more effectively than the other topical anti-histamine formulations⁶. It decreases the mucus discharge in VKC by reducing the goblet cell density in the conjunctiva⁷.

Bepotastine besilate 1.5% was approved by the US Food and Drug Administration in 2009 for the treatment of ocular itching associated with allergic conjunctivitis, with twice a day dosing in patients 2 years of age and older⁸.

Multiple anti-inflammatory effects have been demonstrated due to its antihistaminic action. *in vitro* studies suggest that bepotastine specifically suppresses proinflammatory cytokine production by keratinocytes, including inhibition of CD54 expression. Bepotastine inhibits IL-5 action or production which is a key agent in promoting eosinophil activation and eosinophil-mediated inflammation. It stabilizes mast cell and inhibits production of leukotrienes B4.

The purpose of this study is to delve more into these dual acting drugs which are available over the counter and provide instant relief to the patient. Very few studies were done in vernal kerato conjunctivitis comparing efficacy of 0.1% Olopatadine and Bepotastine 1.5% in India.

Materials and Methods: This is a Prospective, Randomised, Observational Study conducted at the department of Ophthalmology of a tertiary eye care hospital. 50 cases of newly diagnosed VKC who were more than 5 years of age were selected for the study. Cases who were already on treatment and cases who were having other ocular disorders, Contact lens users and those whose parents and gaurdians had not given consent were excluded. 50 cases selected were randomly divided based on even and Odd MR No.

into 2 groups. Informed consent obtained from parents of all patients. All were examined by an experienced Ophthalmologist using, Snellen's chart, Slit Lamp, Direct Ophthalmoscope, 90 D Slit lamp Bio microscopy . Baseline score were recorded based on Symptoms like Itching, Watering, Redness, FB sensation and Signs like Hyperaemia, Discharge, Papillae on tarsal conjunctiva and Tranta's spot at the Limbus.

Group A consist of patients who were given Olopatadine eye drops to be instilled 3 times daily for 6 weeks. Group B consist of VKC patients who were

given Bepotastine eye drops to be instilled twice daily for 6 weeks. Both group were called for Follow up after 1 week, 2 weeks and 6 weeks. Patients were asked about relief from Symptomatology and examined for regression of Signs at each visit according to VKC score.

Results: 50 cases selected for study were aged between 5-15years. 5-10 years there were 36 cases and between 10-15 years 14 cases were there. Sex distribution was 39 males and 11 females.

ITCHING SCORES:

Itching	Group A (mean score)	Group B (mean score)	Students T test (P value)
Baseline	2.16	2.32	0.45
1 st follow up(1 st week)	1.68	1.6	0.76
2 nd follow up(2 nd week)	1.16	0.7	0.005*
3 rd follow up(6 th week)	0.68	0.6	0.73

SCORING FOR TEARING/WATERING

Tearing	Group A (mean score)	Group B (mean score)	Students T test (P value)
Baseline	2.08	1.8	0.41
1 st follow up(1 st week)	1.64	1.36	0.3
2 nd follow up(2 nd week)	1.08	0.48	0.001***
3 rd follow up(6 th week)	0.32	0.12	0.16

Scoring for Foreign Body sensation

Foreign Body sensation	Group A (mean score)	Group B (mean score)	Students T test (P value)
Baseline	2.04	1.84	0.57
1 st follow up(1 st week)	1.6	1.6	1
2 nd follow up(2 nd week)	0.84	0.44	0.05*
3 rd follow up(6 th week)	0.36	0.08	0.05*

SCORING FOR CONJUNCTIVAL HYPERAEMIA

Conjunctival Hyperaemia	Group A (mean score)	Group B (mean score)	Students T test (P value)
Baseline	2.48	2.4	0.69
1 st follow up(1 st week)	1.68	1	0.001***
2 nd follow up(2 nd week)	0.68	0.24	0.003**
3 rd follow up(6 th week)	0	0	-

SCORING FOR PAPILLARY HYPERTROPHY

Papillary Hypertrophy	Group A (mean score)	Group B (mean score)	Students T test (P value)
Baseline	1.8	1.84	0.88
1 st follow up(1 st week)	1.16	1.24	0.79
2 nd follow up(2 nd week)	0.76	0.8	0.82
3 rd follow up(6 th week)	0.36	0.56	0.16

Symptomatology like itching, Watering, FB sensation got relieved and regression of signs like Hyperaemia and discharge got reduced in Group B by 2nd visit ie after 2 weeks which statistically significant .

In Group A cases it took longer for regression of signs. They showed improvement after 6 weeks.

Symptoms like FB sensation because of Hypertrophied Papillae, not get completely regressed in both Groups.

DISCUSSION:

Subhabrata Parida et al⁹ studied 128 cases of VKC. one group received Bepotastine 1.5% eye drops and another received Olopatadine 0.1% eye drops. On day three group receiving Bepotastine eye drops was relieved of symptoms like itching, watering and regression of signs like Hyperaemia, Papillary reaction. Group receiving Olopatadine took 2 weeks for same action. Present study also shown Bepotastine superiority over Olopatadine.

Durga Vasantha Laxmi Jasthi et al¹⁰ studied 200 cases of VKC , One group of 100 received

Bepotastine eye drops and another 100 received Olopatadine eye drops. After a week group treated with Bepotastine was relieved of redness completely whereas group treated with Olopatadine only 80% was relieved of symptoms. But after 4 weeks results was equal in both groups. This is also consistent with present study.

Vadlakonda Shruthi, R Neha Reddy et al¹¹, studied 50 patients of VKC, divided into two groups. One group received Bepotastine eye drops and other group received Olopatadine eye drops for 8 weeks. Bepotastine group showed immediate response within 2 weeks in Symptomatology of Itching watering and regression of Signs like Hyperaemia and Papillary reaction. But after 8 weeks both groups showed equal results with no statistical significance. The result in present study is similar.

Saurabh Tripathi, Nidhi, Amaresh et al¹², studied 210 patients of VKC . Divided patients into 3 groups of 70 each. Group A received Alcaftadine eye drops, Group B received Bepotastine eye drops and Group C received Olopatadine eye drops. After 2 weeks group receiving Alcaftadine and Bepotastine showed

improvement in Symptoms and signs. Whereas group receiving Olopatadine took longer time for alleviation of symptoms and signs. This again similar to present study.

CONCLUSION

It is concluded in Present study and Various other studies done elsewhere that Bepotastine eye drops are superior in controlling Symptomatology like Itching, Watering and redness within short duration of usage. Regression of Signs like Hyperaemia, Discharge and FB sensation also got relieved early by Bepotastine eye drops when compared to Olopatadine eye drops.

Institutional Ethics Committee approval obtained.

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